

IMPLICATIONS OF MEDICALIZATION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS ON TRADITIONAL MEDICINE AND SOCIO-CULTURAL VALUES IN THE RURAL COMMUNITIES OF NORTH-WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICTS OF AKWA IBOM STATE

By

Nkanta, Nsikan Clement

Department of Sociology, Ritman University,
Ikot Ekpene Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Email: nsynkanta@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study focused on the effects of medicalization of social problems on traditional medicine and socio-cultural values in rural communities in North-West Senatorial district of Akwa Ibom state. To ascertain these effects, three research objectives and questions were formulated, and a review of relevant literature was done. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 363 respondents who identified themselves as constant apologist of traditional or modern medicine respectively in health centers and traditional birth homes. The conflict theory was employed to explain the effects of medicalization of social problems on traditional medicine and socio-cultural values in rural communities. The biodata of respondents were statistically presented while data associated with dependent and independent variables were presented in table and chi-square. Based on the outcome of the analyzed data, the study concluded that medicalization of social problems should not be ignored given its destructive implications for traditional medicine which was discovered to be the primary health option in the rural communities, and detrimental to the socio-cultural values in the societies. The study made recommendations aimed at addressing the effects of medicalization of social problems in relations to traditional medicine and socio-cultural values in the rural communities and beyond.

Key words: medicalization, traditional medicine, and socio-cultural values.

INTRODUCTION

Medicalization of social problems has attracted the attention of many scholars and authorities resulting in many definitions. However, amid the proliferation of definitions, there is no dissenting opinion regarding medicalization as oppositional to native approach to health challenges. Following this perspective, Moncrieff (2020) described medicalization as the process of thinking about social issues as individual pathologies thereby shifting the focus from social factors to the biology or psychology of individuals, and suggesting reliance on pharmaceutical authorities. Buried in this reasoning is that, matters that would have been blamed on the failure of the individual actor or the society to exhibit the normative behavior and control is rather blamed, explained in medical terms. Kirli and Kaya (2025), saw

medicalization as consisting in treating a normal biological process or behavior as medical issues, it involves subjecting realities and experiences of normal life to medical or pharmaceutical interventions or approaches. As a concept, it was first applied by social scientists to discuss the tendency of medical institutions and professionals to describe non-medical behavior. Generally speaking, it looks at how medical regulations replaced supposedly social control institutions (law, church, family, custom and tradition) in the management of deviance or how deviance gradually changed from crime to sickness in the society” or as a process where non-medical problems are defined and treated as medical issues, often leading to pathologization of human differences and individualization of problems while minimizing social and political context. This paved way for departure from the normative behavior in the rural communities to subsumed under the domineering influence of medicine, and made to accept explanations and solutions to anti-social behavior which ordinarily would have been treated and explained in tandem with socio-cultural procedures. This dominating intention lumped in the medicalization must had motivated conflict theorists to characterize medicalization as the suppression of other social institutions by medical professionals by creating the impression that, the society has no alternative approach to health issues but medicine. This reveals the source of hatred and disdained that traditional medicine experience despite its authority in the rural communities and anticipating modern medicine in chronological description. Halpin and Cortez (2025) saw medicalization as an action or activity undertaken by medical practitioners and allied actors to establish and justify their claim of being capable to replace traditional medicine and addressing all health issues. Though the medical profession has assumed a scientific height that is absent in traditional medicine, yet, it should be noted that there are salient health issues that traditional medicine retains unchallengeable advantage and patronage in line with one of its natural features of not inexplicability in specific situations but fulfilling its purpose.

Despite the multiple opinions on medicalization, this paper describes, medicalization of social problems as a determine endeavor by the progenitors and apologists of modern medicine to diminish the popularity of non-medical and pharmaceutical approaches to health and social issues by characterizing such non-medical option as unscientific. But unscientific in what and whose perspective? It must be acknowledged that health is a relative variable and culture-determined, as such, the procedures for sustaining and protecting health are contingent on the socio-cultural promptings of the immediate environment. Aftercall, traditional medicine has to do with indigenous health practices developed and applied by ancestral people, and transferred from the past to the contemporary generation based on proven cases of efficiency whether orally or in writing. This philosophy aligns with that of the World Health Organization (WHO,2025), in which traditional medicine is described as “ the codified or non-codified systems for health and well-being, comprising practices, skills, knowledge and philosophies originated in different historical and cultural contexts, which are distinct from and pre-dates biomedicine, evolving with science for current use from an experience-based origin, and emphasizes nature-based remedies and holistic, personalized approaches to restore balance between the mind, body and environment”. The National Centre for Complementary and Integrated Health (2023), complemented these expositions by defining traditional medicine as “a vast and diverse body of knowledge, skills, and practices that have been developed and refined over centuries “This definition indicates that, traditional medicine such as Ayurveda and Traditional Chines Medicine

(TCM) thrives on ancestral philosophy like maintaining equilibrium between “life-forces “or “vital energy” in order to live. From these definitions, it is concerning that traditional medicine which existed prior to emergence of modern medicine is now struggling to survive in the face of vivacious competition from modern medicine.

Socio-cultural values could be seen as a system of human and society-oriented behavior, and attitude needed to ensure predictable social interaction. To a large extent, people react to situations based on the value they attach to them. Forsyth, Tanner, and Chapel (2023) are of the opinion that, it is socio-cultural values that influence how people view and interpret the world around them. It means that values constitute the rules and expectance of behavior predicated on shared beliefs within a specific cultural or social group. Or they (values) stipulate the ideal standard of appropriate behavior. Values and norms therefore regulate interactions and perception in communities. It determines whether a society is to embrace a particular option in solving a particular problem and achieving certain goals. Suffice it to say that, socio-cultural values possess inhibitory and excitatory potentials for the proper functioning of any human society. Succinctly speaking, patronage to modern medicine and traditional medicine in the rural communities should be determined by the prevailing socio-cultural values. It is this ideal status that therefore indicts the perception of medicalization a Swiss-knife health approach to the detriment of traditional medicine. Appropriate patronage to traditional medicine and protection of socio-cultural values in the rural communities and other human societies, consists in unraveling the effects of medicalization of social problems on traditional medicine and socio-cultural values. An average rural person is conditioned by the traditions of the community. This provides the moral compass to all and sundry. Values determine the rightness and wrongness of an act. Those who go against the popular values are classified in different derogatory terms. Socio-cultural values in the rural communities therefore constitute the moral mirror of her members. It throws at the individual the exact reflection of his/her behavior.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Medicalization had reduced the influence of traditional medicine and socio-cultural values to an unprecedented low extent, resulting in avoidable prevalence of deviance behavior. There is no human society without rules governing behavior and specific mechanism for checking aberrations. In the rural communities, tradition, custom and norms created, practiced and transferred from one generation to another by the forebears provided the regulatory framework by specifying the acceptable and unacceptable behaviors for an orderly society and social interactions. Medicalization of social problems in the rural communities had disrupted this age-long social control. Resultantly, traditional methods of treating health issues, and correcting anti-social behavior are no longer respected leading to avoidable exorbitant spending on health issues and increase exculpation from punishment for offence committed on the grounds that, the offender is sick and should not be punished for the offence, but rather subjected to medical treatment. This indeed promote criminality and deviance. It was these issues that motivated this study in order to unbundle the effects of medicalization of social problems on traditional medicine and socio-cultural values through recommendations made after the analysis of the reactions of respondents

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main object of this study was to examine the effects of medicalization of social problems on the traditional Medicine and socio-socio-cultural values,

1. To examine whether medicalization affected patronage to traditional medicine in rural communities.
2. To examine whether societal perception of traditional medicine promoted medicalization of social problems in the rural communities.
3. To examine whether medicalization of social problem is anti-thetical to socio-cultural values.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Does medicalization of social problems affect the use of traditional medicine in the rural communities?
2. Does societal perception of traditional medicine promote medicalization of social problems in rural communities?
3. Is medicalization of social problems anti-thetical to socio-cultural values in the rural communities?

METHODOLOGY

The simple random sampling procedure was used in selecting a representative sample of respondents within the study community; Etim Ekpo, Ika, Essien Udim, Abak, Ukanafun and Oruk Anam all in Akwa Ibom State. 363 collated questionnaires out of the 400 administered, were analyzed and presented in tables while variables associated with requestions were analyzed using chi-square. Respondents were persons between 30 and 60 years plus. Being qualitative research the biodata of respondents was noted and presented.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

TABLE 1: BIODATA OF RESPONDENT BY AGE

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
30-40	52	14.33
40-50	78	21.49
50-60	72	19.83
above 60	161	44.35
TOTAL	363	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The above table shows that 161 (44.35%) respondents were above 60 years old. 72 (19.83%) were between 50 and 60 years of age. 78 (21.49%) were between 40 and 50 years of age and 52(14.33%) were between 30 and 40 years of age.

TABLE 2: EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
SSCE/WASCE	95	26.17
HND	79	21.76

B.SC	123	33.88
MASTERS/PH.D.	66	18.18
TOTAL	363	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The table above shows that 66(18.18%) respondents were, M. Sc/Ph.D holders. 123(33.88%) were B.Sc holders. 79(21.76%) were HND holders and 95(26.17%) were SSCE holders.

TABLE 3: RELIGION

RELIGION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Christianity	225	61.98
Traditional Worshipers	72	19.83
Others	66	18.18
TOTAL	363	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The table above shows that 225(61.98%) respondents were Christians. 72(19.83%) were traditional worshipers and 66(18.18%) were Others.

DATA PRESENTATION/ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

Does the medicalization of social problems affect patronage to traditional medicine in your community?

Response	Frequency
Yes	241
No	122

Source: Field Survey 2025

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 241 respondents strongly believes that medicalization of social problems highly affects patronage to traditional medicine in their communities, while 122 of the respondents believes it does not.

Does you or your family member subscribe to traditional medicine?

Response	Frequency
Yes	221
No	142

Source: Field Survey 2025

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 221 respondents strongly believes that their family members subscribes more to traditional medicines compared to modern medicines, while 142 of the respondents does not.

Traditional medicine is more accessible to modern medicine?

Response	Frequency
Yes	252
No	111

Source: Field Survey 2025

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 252 respondents strongly believes that traditional medicines are more accessible to modern medicines, while 142 of the respondents believes modern medicines are more accessible to traditional medicines

	Yes	No	Total
Q1	241	122	363
Q2	221	142	363
Q3	252	111	363
Total	714	375	1089

Source: Field Survey 2025

X-squared = 6.0276, df = 2, p-value = 0.0491. with df = 2, the p-value < 0.005 (Significant)

CONCLUSION: The results above shows that there is a statistically significant association between the question asked and respondents' answers and this suggests that patronage of traditional medicine is not uniform: while accessibility and usage are strongly affirmed, the influence of medicalization is perceived somewhat differently.

(PERCEPTION OF MEDICALIZATION)

1. Does societal perception of traditional medicine promote medicalization of social problems in your community?

Response	Frequency
Yes	251
No	112

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 251 respondents strongly believes that societal perception of traditional medicine promotes medicalization of social problems in their community, while 112 of the respondents believes otherwise.

Are you more comfortable with traditional medicine than modern medicine?

Response	Frequency
Yes	237
No	126

Source: Field Survey 2025

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 237 respondents strongly believes that they are more comfortable traditional medicine than modern medicine, while 126 of the respondents prefer otherwise.

3. Do you have faith in modern medicine than traditional?

Response	Frequency
Yes	102
No	261

Source: Field Survey 2025

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 102 respondents have faith in modern medicine than traditional medicine, while 261 of the respondents have faith in traditional medicine than modern medicine.

	Yes	No	Total
Q1	251	112	363

Q2	237	126	363
Q3	102	261	363
Total	590	499	1089

X-squared = 150.26, df = 2, p-value = 2.2e-16

With df = 2, the p-value < 0.005 (Significant)

CONCLUSION: There is a very strong association between the type of question asked and how respondents answer. Overall, the responses show that community perception strongly favors traditional medicine — people believe it promotes medicalization, they are more comfortable with it, and they have greater faith in traditional medicine than in modern medicine.

RESEACH QUESTION THREE: Is medicalization of social problems anti-thetical to socio cultural values in your community?

Response	Frequency
Yes	236
No	127

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 236 respondents believes medicalization of social problems is anti-thetical to socio cultural values in their community, while 127 of the respondents believes otherwise.

Are there obvious alterations in community cohesion inspired by the adoption of medical practices?

Response	Frequency
Yes	205
No	158

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 205 respondents believes there are obvious alterations in community cohesion inspired by the adoption of medical practices, while 158 of the respondents believes otherwise.

Do traditional healing processes promote your cultural nativity?

Response	Frequency
Yes	208
No	155

Interpretation: The table above shows the distribution of responses from respondents which 208 respondents believes that traditional healing processes promotes cultural nativity, while 158 of the respondents do not belief that traditional healing processes promotes cultural nativity.

	Yes	No	Total
Q1	251	112	363
Q2	237	126	363
Q3	102	261	363
Total	590	499	1089

X-squared = 6.689, df =

2, p-value = 0.03528 With df = 2, the p-value < 0.005 (Significant)

CONCLUSION:

There is a significant association between the type of question asked and the responses given. Hence, the results suggest that people in the community perceive modern medical practices as influencing socio-cultural values and community cohesion, with varying levels of agreement across the questions.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS:

Arising from analysis of the research questions, one observed the following:

Responses to 'does medicalization of social problem affect patronage to traditional medicine'-241 out of 363 said yes to while 122 said No. meaning that, medicalization impeded patronage to traditional medicine. Respondents' reaction to the question "does societal perception of traditional medicine promotes medicalization"-251 said yes while 112 opposed. Meaning that perception affected the use of traditional medicine. 236 said yes against 127 that said no in response to the question is medicalization anti-thetical to socio-cultural value. Findings here affirm that socio-cultural values suffered from medicalization.

CONCLUSION:

From the above, this paper concluded that medicalization of social problem has had severe effects on traditional medicine and socio-cultural values, a critical scenario indeed. Historically, traditional medicine is the closest health option to the rural dwellers. In view of the scarcity of health facilities and obvious negative attitude of authorities to the provision of critical public infrastructure like hospitals, clinics, health Centre and the gross insufficiency of healthcare, the rural communities should be assisted through the development of their native approach to sustaining and protecting health. Medialization of social problem is therefore unnecessary to the rural folks. It should be noted that, while this paper is not unmindful of the successes recorded by medicine in the human societies, traditional medicine is glued to the culture of the people especially those in the rural societies and should be encouraged

RECOMMENDATIONS:

There should be de-medicalization of social problems in order to encourage patronage to native approach to health. They should be sensitization and re-orientation in the rural areas to correct their perception of medicalization of medicalization as a Swiss-knife. Communities should strengthen their socio-cultural value by re-emphasizing their traditions, customs and norms in order to maintain their indigenous control mechanism.

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